

Supplementary Material

Appendix I

Experiment 1: Effect of stocking rate on dairy farm efficiency. Ten farmlet systems were established at No. 2 Dairy, Dexcel (Hamilton, New Zealand), with Holstein Friesian (**HF**) dairy cows randomly assigned to one of 5 duplicated treatment groups with increasing stocking rate of 2.2, 2.7, 3.1, 3.7, and 4.3 cows/ha (Macdonald et al., 2008). A subset of cows from the 2.2, 3.1, and 4.3 cows/ha treatment groups had detailed measurements, with only these data included in the database. Total annual feed allowances of approximately 8.1, 5.8, and 4.2 tonnes (t) DM/cow per yr were created by stocking the farmlet systems with 500 kg HF cows at a target of 62, 90, and 120 kg LW/t DM per yr.

Experiments 2 to 4: Overseas versus New Zealand Holstein-Friesian genetics. The responses of HF cows of either overseas (**OS**; North American/Dutch) or New Zealand (**NZ**) genetic origin were compared under different nutritional management treatments to determine genetic x environmental interactions. Cows of either OS or NZ genetic origin were fed either grazed pasture or a total mixed ration (**TMR**) with corn and grass silage and concentrate in a 2 x 2 factorial design for experiment 2 (Kolver et al., 2002), followed by a 2 x 3 factorial design for experiments 3 and 4 with cows grazing pasture with increasing levels of concentrate (0, 3, or 6 kg DM/cow per d; Roche et al., 2006a).

In **experiment 2**, held at the Dexcel No.1 Dairy (Hamilton, New Zealand), the dietary treatments had been imposed for 2 seasons prior to the 2000/2001 season when the data used herein were collected (Kolver et al., 2002). Treatment groups were NZ TMR-fed (n = 14), OS TMR-fed (n = 14), NZ pasture-fed (n = 14), and OS pasture-fed (n = 13). The TMR-fed groups were kept outdoors but confined to one of five paddocks (0.25 ha/paddock) and a free-draining concrete feed pad that was used during July, August, and September, with NZ and OS TMR-fed groups kept separately throughout the lactation. The TMR was fed between 0800 and 1000 h and 1500 and 1700 h each day, with the same ration fed to each of the NZ and OS TMR-fed groups to achieve a 10% refusal rate with *ad libitum* intake. Composition of the TMR throughout lactation is detailed in Kolver et al. (2002). During the dry period, both NZ and OS TMR-fed groups were maintained on pasture and 20 d before expected calving date were introduced to a pre-calving TMR in addition to grazed pasture. A small amount of silage was offered to both NZ and OS pasture-fed groups for 2 wk during spring and 3 wk during summer at a rate of 0.5% of BW to maintain post-grazing residual targets.

Experiment 3 was the first season and **experiment 4** was the second season of a two-year experiment from July 2002 to June 2004 at Lye Farm, Dexcel (Hamilton, New Zealand; Roche et al., 2006a). In experiment 3, 54 cows of OS and NZ genetic strains were randomly allocated to 1 of 3 supplementary feeding treatments (0, 3, or 6 kg DM concentrate/cow per d) in a 2 x 3 factorial arrangement to give treatment groups: NZ 0 (n = 9), NZ 3 (n = 9), NZ 6 (n = 9), OS 0 (n = 8), OS 3 (n = 10), and OS 6 (n = 9). In experiment 4, 59 cows of OS and NZ genetic origin were re-randomized

into the same 3 treatments in a 2 x 3 factorial arrangement (32 cows from experiment 3 and 27 additional cows), with treatment groups: NZ 0 (n = 10), NZ 3 (n = 10), NZ 6 (n = 10), OS 0 (n = 9), OS 3 (n = 10), and OS 6 (n = 10). The NZ 3, NZ 6, OS 3, and OS 6 groups received their supplementary feed in a concentrate pellet form equally split in two feeds daily during milking for their entire lactation. For 15 d prior to the expected calving date, all cows were offered 2 kg DM/cow per d of concentrate, whilst post-calving the NZ 3 and OS 3 were offered their full allowance of 3 kg DM/cow per d concentrate and the NZ 6 and OS 6 cows were offered 3 kg DM/cow per d, increasing by 0.5 kg DM/cow per d over the 6 d, to reach their allowance of 6 kg DM/cow/d (Kolver et al., 2005, 2006; Roche et al., 2006a).

Experiment 5: Effect of pre-calving pasture allowance. Fifty-two multiparous HF cows predicted to calve over a 21 d period were randomly assigned into 1 of 4 dietary treatments at 27 d pre-calving (n = 13/group; Roche et al., 2005). The experiment was conducted Lye Farm, Dexcel during July and August 2003. The four dietary treatment groups were offered 6.5, 10.1, 14.6, or 24.1 kg DM/cow per d, designed to achieve a pre-calving pasture DMI of 5.5, 8.0, 10.5, and 13.0 kg DM/cow per d, respectively. Actual DMI for the respective treatment groups were 5.4, 8.2, 10.0, and 11.0 kg DM/cow per d. Cows from all treatment groups were grazed together as a single herd post-calving and fed *ad libitum* fresh pasture.

Experiment 6: Effect of lipid supplementation pre- and post-calving. This experiment was conducted Lye Farm, Dexcel during July and August 2003. Twenty-six multiparous HF cows were randomly assigned to either 8 kg DM/cow per d pasture and 540g/d Hyprofat (a palm fatty acid distillate; Bonimex BV) or 8 kg DM/cow per d pasture and 600 g/d RI-CLA (RI-CLA; Bioproducts Inc.) whereby, lipid doses provided 520 g fatty acids/d (n = 13/group; Kay et al., 2006). These two treatment groups were compared with the medium (8.2 kg DM/cow per d) group from experiment 5 (Roche et al., 2005), which served as the control. Treatments were initiated at 27 d prior to expected calving date and continued to 36 d post-calving.

Experiment 7: Effect of pre-calving and post-calving pasture allowance. Sixty-eight multiparous HF cows predicted to calve in the first 21 d of the calving season were randomly assigned to either a high (11.9 kg DM/cow per d) or low (4.8 kg DM/cow per d) pasture intake from 29 d pre-calving (Burke and Roche, 2007). The experiment was conducted at Dexcel from July to September 2004. At calving, cows were randomly allocated to either high (13.5 kg DM/cow per d) or low (8.6 kg DM/cow per d) pasture intake for 35 d post-calving to complete the 2 x 2 factorial arrangement of treatment groups (n = 17/group). Following the post-calving treatment period, all cows were offered the same feed allowance.

Experiment 8: Altering proportion of structural carbohydrate and nonfibre carbohydrate pre- and post-calving. Sixty-eight multiparous HF and HF x Jersey crossbred (**HF x J**) dairy cows due to calve within a 21 d period were randomly assigned into 1 of 2 pre-partum dietary treatment groups (n = 34/group) at approximately 36 d pre-calving (Roche et al., 2010). The experiment was conducted at Lye Farm, DairyNZ from July to September 2005. Pre-calving dietary treatment groups received

either pasture and pasture silage or an equivalent amount of energy in the form of 3 kg DM/cow per d of a concentrate pellet, designed to supply cows with 110% of their calculated pre-partum energy requirements (96 MJ of ME/cow per d; Roche et al., 2005). At calving, cows were randomly allocated to 1 of 2 post-calving dietary treatment groups (n = 34) offered either pasture and pasture silage or an equivalent amount of energy in the form of 5 kg DM/cow per d of a concentrate pellet, to give a 2 x 2 factorial arrangement (Roche et al., 2010). The concentrate pellets were introduced gradually over a 3-d period and offered in 2 equal portions at the a.m. and p.m. milking, with post-calving dietary treatments continuing for 35 d.

Experiment 9: Effect of long-term infusion of ghrelin or obestatin. The experiment was conducted at Lye Farm, DairyNZ from July to September 2006, which involved 3 treatment groups however, as hormone treatments Obestatin and Ghrelin were used, only data collected from the control group were included in the database (n = 17).

Experiment 10: Effect of milking frequency and duration. This experiment was conducted at Lye Farm, DairyNZ from July to November 2009, involving the random assignment of 150 HF and HF x J dairy cows into 1 of 5 treatments immediately post-calving (Phyn et al., 2014). Treatment groups were: twice daily milking for the entire lactation (control group, n = 30), once-daily milking for either 21 d (n = 30) or 42 d (n = 30) post-calving, and thrice-daily milking for either 21 d (n = 28) or 42 d (n = 32) post-calving. Following completion of their milking frequency challenge, individual cows in the once- and thrice-daily treatment groups were moved into the twice-daily milking group and all cows grazed together for the remainder of the experimental period. Cows were offered 2 kg DM/cow per d of pelleted concentrate pre-calving and 4 kg DM/cow per d post-calving.

Experiment 11: Effect of body condition score at calving. The experiment was conducted at Lye Farm, DairyNZ from January to September 2011. Sixty HF and HF x J dairy cows of mixed age were randomly allocated to 1 of 3 treatment groups (n = 20/group) beginning 1 February, whereby daily feed allowances were manipulated to create high, medium, and low BCS groups before the end of lactation, targeting BCS of 5.0, 4.0 and 3.0, respectively (Roche et al., 2013b). Following drying off, cows were offered pasture and supplements to support foetal growth and a gain of 0.5 BCS units prior to calving, with the intention of a mean BCS at calving of 5.5, 4.5, and 3.5 for the high, medium, and low groups, respectively. Following calving, all cows were offered the same feed allowance.

Experiment 12: Effect of post-calving non-steroidal anti-inflammatory treatment (2011). The experiment was conducted at Scott Farm, DairyNZ (Hamilton, New Zealand) from May to October 2011, involving 213 multiparous HF and HF x J dairy cows (Priest et al., 2013). Cows were blocked for calving date and PMN percentage at 14 d post-calving before random allocation into either the control (n = 109) or non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (**NSAID**; n = 104) group. Cows in the NSAID group received 3 injections of carprofen (Carpreive LA; 50 mg carprofen/mL Norbrook New Zealand Ltd.) at 3 d intervals (each injection = 1.4 mg carprofen/kg of BW; 1 mL of carprofen/35 kg of BW) between 21 and 31 d post-calving.

Experiment 13: Effect of post-calving non-steroidal anti-inflammatory treatment (2012).

This experiment was conducted at Whareroa Dairy Farm (Hawera, New Zealand) from July to November 2012, involving 639 dairy cows of mixed age and breed (predominantly HF and HF x J; Meier et al., 2014). Cows were allocated within a randomized block design to 1 of 3 groups as they calved. Control group cows (n = 221) were not treated, the early group cows (n = 214) received an injection on 1, 3, and 5 d post-calving, and the late group cows (n = 204) received an injection on 19, 21, and 23 d post-calving. Injections were subcutaneous treatments of 1.4 mg/kg of BW of carprofen (Carprieve LA; Norbrook Ltd.).

Experiment 14: Effect of late lactation once-daily milking. During late lactation (mean = 175 DIM), 52 pregnant HF cows were randomly assigned to either once-daily or twice-daily milking (n = 26/group) for approximately 12 wk until dry-off (mean = 259 DIM; Grala et al., 2016). The experiment was conducted at Lye Farm, DairyNZ from January to September 2013. All cows were previously milked twice daily from calving in July – August 2012. Cows were dried-off individually based on milk production and BCS, with the final dry-off date 56 d before the planned start of calving in July 2013. Following calving, all cows were milked twice daily and managed as a single herd.

Experiment 15: Effect of pre-calving body condition score and feeding level. This experiment was conducted at Scott farm, DairyNZ between January and October 2013, whereby 150 mixed age and breed (HF, HF x J, and Jersey; J) cows were randomly assigned to 1 of 6 treatment groups (n = 25/group) in a 2 x 3 factorial arrangement (Roche et al., 2015). Treatment groups had 2 pre-calving BCS categories of 4.0 and 5.0 (n = 75/BCS group) and 3 levels of energy intake during the 3 wk prior to expected calving date of 75, 100, and 125% of estimated energy requirements (1.05 MJ/kg BW^{0.75}). Cows in the 2 BCS groups were managed to achieve their BCS target at dry-off. Cows were then fed to maintain their BCS target until approximately 23 d pre-calving when they were offered their assigned feeding level treatments. Following calving, all cows were managed as a single herd and offered the same feed allowance.

Experiment 16: Effect of strategies to gain body condition score during the far-off and close-up nonlactating periods. One hundred and fifty dairy cows of mixed age and breed (HF, HF x J, and J) were allocated randomly to 1 of 2 treatment groups (n = 75/group) with all cows dried off approximately 80 d prior to calving (Roche et al., 2017a). This experiment was conducted at Lye farm, DairyNZ between January and October 2014. During late lactation (~215 DIM), feeding levels were manipulated to achieve BCS of either 4.25 or 5.0 at dry-off. Subsequently, cows were either over-fed or control-fed, respectively, during the far-off nonlactating period (i.e. approximately 80 to 40 d prior to calving) to achieve a similar BCS pre-calving. During the 3 wk before calving (i.e. close-up period), cows within each BCS gain group were randomly assigned to 1 of 3 feeding levels (either 65, 90 or 120% of estimated ME requirements; 1.05 MJ/kg BW^{0.75}) to complete the 2 x 3 factorial arrangement

of treatment design. Following calving, all cows were managed as a single herd and offered fresh pasture supplemented with pasture silage.

Experiment 17: Effect of feeding zeolite pre-calving. This experiment was undertaken at Lye farm, DairyNZ between June 2016 and February 2017. During late gestation, 50 parous HF and HF x J cows were randomly allocated to 1 of 2 treatment groups, either control or zeolite fed (n = 25/group; Crookenden et al., 2020; Phyn et al., in preparation). From 14 d before their expected calving date, cows were offered a common pasture allowance but were individually fed 2 kg DM/cow per d of corn silage either with 500 g/cow/d of synthetic zeolite A (Optimate MF+, Blue Pacific minerals; equivalent to 400 g of sodium aluminosilicate) or without zeolite (control). Zeolite feeding ceased at calving, and all cows were managed similarly post-calving.

Experiment 18: Effect of Imrestor dose rate and timing. One hundred and seventy-three, mixed age HF and HF x J cows were randomly allocated to 1 of 7 treatment groups (n ≥ 23/ group) in late gestation (Crookenden et al., 2021). This experiment was undertaken at Lye Farm, DairyNZ between June and September 2017. Treatments involved a subcutaneous injection at 1 wk prior to expected calving day (d -7) and on the day of calving (d 0) of either sterile saline (0.9% NaCl) or Imrestor (pegbovigrastim available as Imrestor™, Elanco) in a full dose (15 mg pegbovigrastim in 2.7 mL; equivalent to approximately 28 µg pegbovigrastim/kg BW in 535 kg LW cows), half dose (0.5; 1.35 mL), or quarter dose (0.25; 0.675mL). Treatment groups were: saline/saline, 0.25/0.25, 0.5/0.5, full/full, full/saline, saline/full, and saline/half for the d -7/0 doses. All cows grazed fresh pasture (11.9 MJ ME/kg DM; 16.5% DM) in the same paddock and were supplemented with corn silage (2.5 kg DM/cow per d; 10.4 MJ ME/kg DM; 36% DM) and pasture silage (approximately 20% of the diet; 11.9 MJ ME/kg DM; 29% DM) as required if insufficient fresh pasture was available to meet grazing residual targets; they also received 80% palm kernel expeller/20% tapioca mix (1.5 kg DM/cow per d; 6.8 MJ ME/kg DM; 93% DM) following calving.

To replicate standard farm practice, cows received magnesium supplementation from 2-3 wk pre-calving by dusting the pasture pre-grazing with magnesium oxide (CausMag; 55% magnesium) at a dose of 80 to 100 g/cow per d. In addition, cows received 200 g/cow per d of calcium carbonate post-calving for 4 d during the colostrum period.

Experiment 19: Effect of high or low fertility breeding value. This experiment was undertaken at the AgResearch Tokanui Research farm (Waikato, New Zealand). Detailed descriptions of the breeding programme used to create a herd of HF cows with divergent Fertility Breeding Value (FBV) are outlined in Meier et al. (2017; 2021) and Grala et al. (2021). Briefly, cows of High/Positive (POS) and Low/Negative (NEG) FBV were contract bred using artificial insemination to corresponding POS and NEG FBV sires. A total of 640 heifer calves were collected between June and September 2015 following farmer-reported birth of a heifer calf. As of January 2017, a total of 524 heifers were in the research herd (POS = +5% FBV, n = 275; NEG = -5% FBV, n = 249) and their data between January

and October 2017 were collated for the database herein. Cows calved for the first time between July and September 2017 and were grazed in two herds (balanced for calving date and FBV group).

Experiment 20: Effect of zeolite dose and duration. This experiment (Phyn et al. in preparation) was undertaken at Lye farm, DairyNZ between June and December 2018. During late gestation, 92 parous HF and HF x J cows were randomly allocated to either an untreated control group (n=20 cows) or 1 of 6 zeolite dose x duration treatment groups (n=12 cows each) in a 3 x 2 factorial arrangement: doses of either 250, 500 or 750 g synthetic zeolite A/cow/d (Optimate MF+, Blue Pacific Minerals; equivalent to 200, 400 or 600 g of sodium aluminosilicate, respectively) for durations of either 10 or 21 (± 1.5) d before expected individual calving date. Cows were enrolled into the trial twice weekly (either Monday or Thursday) when they reached 21 ± 1.5 d before their expected calving date. Accordingly, zeolite dose x duration treatments commenced on either Monday or Thursday to target pre-allocated durations of either 10 or 21 ± 1.5 d.

Groups were balanced on expected calving date, parity, previous milk production, BW and BCS. The daily dose of zeolite was mixed with corn silage (5 kg wet weight/cow per d; 10.5 MJ ME/kg DM; 33% DM) and fed individually to the treatment cows once-daily in a covered concrete feeding facility in the mornings before a fresh allocation of pasture. The control cows, along with cows enrolled in the 10 d pre-calving duration groups that were yet to begin their treatment period, received the same individual allowance of corn silage without zeolite supplement. Zeolite supplementation ceased at calving. Before calving, control and treatment groups were replicated evenly across four grazing management groups (n=23 cows each) and offered the same allowance of pasture (11.7 MJ ME/kg DM; 16% DM). After calving, cows were managed similarly in the one group, grazed fresh pasture supplemented with corn silage (3 kg DM/cow per d), and either pasture silage (10.7 MJ ME/kg DM; 40% DM) or palm kernel expeller (3 kg DM/cow per d; 5.4 MJ ME/kg DM; 86% DM), or grazed plantain (11.0 MJ ME/kg DM; 13% DM) as required if insufficient fresh pasture was available to meet grazing residual targets.

Cows received magnesium supplementation from 2-3 wk pre-calving by dusting the pasture pre-grazing with magnesium oxide (CausMag; 55% magnesium) at a dose of 80 to 100 g/cow per d. In addition, cows received 200 g/cow per d of calcium carbonate post-calving for 4 d during the colostrum period.

Blood sampling and laboratory analyses

Blood sampling. All experiments contained at least one blood sampling time point within the period approximately 4 wk pre- and 5 wk post-calving, where d 0 is the day of calving. Blood was collected by coccygeal venipuncture into heparinized vacutainers (10 mL), with the sampling frequencies for each of the experiments 2 to 16, 18, and 19 described in publications listed in Table 1. For experiment 1, cows were blood sampled weekly at approximately d -21, -14, -7, 0, 2, 4, 7, and 28. For experiment 17, cows (n = 50) were blood sampled at approximately d -14, -7, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 14, 21, and 28, with a subset of cows (n = 20) additionally sampled daily from approximately 14 d prior to

their expected calving date until d 10 post-calving, and again at d 18 and d 24 (Phyn et al., in preparation). For study 20, cows were blood sampled at approximately d -21, -17, -14, -10, -7, -4, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 10, 14, 17, 21, 28, and 35 (Phyn et al., in preparation).

Following collection, samples were immediately placed on ice before the plasma was aspirated following centrifugation (e.g. 1,500 x g for 12 min at 4°C) and then frozen for subsequent analyses at -20°C. For study 11, samples were also collected in plain tubes with no anticoagulant and were held at ambient temperature following collection for at least 2 h to allow serum to separate before centrifugation (Roche et al., 2013a).

Laboratory analyses: Hormones. In experiments 3 to 7 and 9, plasma concentrations of insulin, growth hormone (**GH**) and IGF were measured in duplicate by double-antibody RIA using the methods validated for bovine by Chagas et al. (2007) at the University of Western Australia (Perth, Australia). Briefly, insulin concentrations ($\mu\text{U/mL}$) in plasma were measured using a modified method of Hales and Randle (1963) as described by Tindal et al. (1978; Kolver et al., 2006). The assay for GH measurement (ng/mL) was conducted as described by Downing et al. (1995). Concentrations of free IGF-1 (ng/mL) in plasma were measured in duplicate using the chloramine-T RIA method as described by Gluckman et al. (1983; Kolver et al., 2006). The acid-ethanol cryoprecipitation method validated for ruminants by Breier et al. (1991) was used to minimize interference by binding proteins (Kolver et al., 2006).

In experiments 5, 6, 7 and 9, leptin concentrations (ng/mL) were also measured as described by Blache et al. (2000). In experiment 14, insulin ($\mu\text{U/mL}$) was measured in duplicate using the Porcine Insulin RIA Kit (PI-12K, Merck Millipore) and leptin concentrations (ng/mL) were determined using the Bovine LEP ELISA kit (SEA084Bo, USCNK) as described by Grala et al. (2016).

Metabolites, minerals, and liver enzymes. Plasma samples were used for all of the following methods, except for experiment 11 whereby plasma was used for analysis of non-esterified fatty acids (**NEFA**) but serum samples were used for all other analyses.

In experiments 1 to 8, concentrations of NEFA (mmol/L ; commercial colorimetric method kit, Wako), BHB (mmol/L ; BHB dehydrogenase assay), glucose (mmol/L ; hexokinase method), urea (mmol/L ; urease hydrolysis method), calcium (**Ca**; mmol/L ; o-cresolphthalein complexone method), and magnesium (**Mg**; mmol/L ; xylidyl blue reaction) were measured by Alpha Scientific Ltd. (Hamilton, New Zealand) using a Hitachi 717 analyzer (Roche) at 30°C. Concentrations of aspartate aminotransferase (**AST**; IU/L ; IFCC UV test measuring catalyzing activity of transamination of L-aspartate to oxaloacetate) and glutamate dehydrogenase (**GDH**; IU/L ; catalyzing activity of NADH-dependent conversion of α -ketoglutarate to glutamate) were also measured in experiments 1, 2, 3 and 5. Albumin (g/L ; citrate buffer reagent) was measured in experiments 1, 2, 7 and 8, and total protein (g/L ; biuret reaction method) was also measured in studies 1, 2, and 7 to estimate globulin concentrations (g/L ; total protein minus albumin). Phosphate (**PO₄**; mmol/L ; ammonium molybdate

UV method), and cholesterol concentrations were measured in studies 1 and 2. In study 9, only NEFA and glucose were measured.

In studies 10 to 20, assays were performed using colorimetric techniques and Roche Modular commercial kits (unless otherwise stated) with a Roche Hitachi Modular P800 analyzer (Roche Diagnostics Corp.) by Gribbles Veterinary Pathology Ltd. (Hamilton, New Zealand) at 37°C. Concentrations of NEFA (mmol/L) were measured using the commercial colorimetric method NEFA C kit (acyl CoA synthase, acyl CoA oxidase method; Wako) for studies 12 to 14, and 17 to 20, and using the commercial NEFA HR2 kit (measuring oxidative condensation of 3-methyl-N-ethyl-N-β hydroxyethyl aniline with 4-aminooantipyrine; Wako) for studies 11, 15, and 16. Concentrations of BHB (mmol/L; reduction of NAD to NADH during oxidation of D-3-hydroxybutyrate to acetoacetate; Ranbut Kit; Randox Laboratories Ltd.) were measured in studies 11, 13, 15 to 20, whereas concentrations of glucose (mmol/L; glucose oxidase method) were also measured in studies 10, 11 and 14. In studies 11 to 13, and 15 to 20, the concentrations of albumin (g/L; bromocresol green reaction at pH 4.1), total protein (g/L; biuret reaction method), globulin (g/L; total protein minus albumin), and Mg (mmol/L; xylydyl blue reaction) were measured. In studies 11 to 13, 15, and 16, concentrations of Ca (mmol/L) were analyzed using the o-cresolphthalein complexone method, whilst for studies 17 to 20, the Ca-NM-BAPTA [5-nitro-5'-methyl-(1,2-bis(o-aminophenoxy)ethan-N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid)] complex reactivity with EDTA method was used. Additionally, urea (mmol/L; urease hydrolysis method), creatinine (μmol/L; enzymatic assay measuring conversion to sarcosine, and liberation of hydrogen peroxide via modified Trinder method to form a quinine imine chromogen) and PO₄ (mmol/L; ammonium molybdate UV method), were measured in studies 11, and 17 to 20; and creatine kinase (IU/L; formation of NADPH from creatine phosphate and ADP method), sodium, potassium, and chloride (mmol/L; Ion Selective Electrode [ISE 900] to determine the membrane EMF proportional to ionic concentration; Roche Diagnostics Corp.), and bicarbonate (mmol/L; reactivity with phosphoenolpyruvate in the presence of phosphoenolpyruvate carboxylase method) were measured in studies 17 to 20.

Liver function markers were measured in the following studies: AST (IU/L; IFCC UV test measuring catalyzing activity of deamination of L-aspartate to oxaloacetate) in studies 10 to 13 and 15 to 20; GDH (IU/L; catalyzing activity of NADH-dependent transamination of α-ketoglutarate to glutamate) in studies 10 to 13 and 16 to 20; gamma-glutamyl transferase (IU/L; production of 5-amino-2-nitrobenzoate) in studies 11 and 17 to 20; and bilirubin (μmol/L; reactivity with 3,5-dichlorophenyl diazonium method) in studies 17 to 20.

For studies 15 to 17, the University of Illinois (Champaign, IL) analyzed plasma cholesterol concentrations using a commercially available fluorometric kit (mmol/L; Cayman Chemical Company). Samples were diluted 1:200 with kit reagents and 50 μL of diluted sample used for the assay. Fluorescence was measured with a fluorometric microplate reader (Biotek Instruments), standard curves

with a 1:2 dilution factor and a zero standard were generated and a linear curve was fitted to the data (Excel; Microsoft Corp.).

Acute phase proteins, cytokines, and inflammation markers. In study 11, serum haptoglobin (**Hp**) concentrations (g/L) were measured using Tridelta Development Ltd. phase kit no. TP801 based on colorimetric determination of peroxidase activity of hemoglobin at low pH. For studies 15 to 17, the University of Illinois (Champaign, IL) analysed plasma IL-1 β , IL-6, and Hp using commercially available bovine ELISA kits (Pierce, Thermo Scientific; GenWay Biotech Inc.; and Life Diagnostics Inc., respectively), whereas total antioxidant capacity (**TAC**) was measured using a commercially available colorimetric kit (Cayman Chemical Company). Assays were followed according to manufacturer protocols as described in Roche et al. (2015): with a total of 100 μ L of undiluted sample used for each of the IL-1 β and IL-6 assays; samples were diluted 1:2,000 with kit reagents and 100 μ L of diluted sample used for the Hp assay; and samples were diluted 1:20 with kit reagents and 10 μ L of diluted sample used for the TAC assay. Absorbance was read with a microplate spectrophotometer (Biotek Instruments), and standard curves with a 1:2 dilution factor and a zero standard were generated for each plate using a 4-parameter logistic curve to fit the IL-1 β and IL-6 data [Gen5 (v2.0) software; Biotek Instruments] and a linear curve to fit the Hp and TAC data (Excel; Microsoft Corp.). Reactive oxygen species were also measured in studies 15 to 17 using a commercially available fluorometric kit (total reactive oxygen species and reactive nitrogen species, including hydrogen peroxide, nitric oxide, peroxy radical, and peroxy nitrite anion, measured by oxidation of DCFH to fluorescent DCF; Cell Biolabs Inc.). Assays were followed according to manufacturer protocols as described in Roche et al. (2015), using a total of 50 μ L of undiluted sample. Fluorescence was measured with a fluorometric microplate reader (Biotek Instruments), standard curves with a 1:2 dilution factor and a zero standard were generated and a linear curve was fitted to the data (Excel; Microsoft Corp.).

Liver biopsies and laboratory analyses.

Liver tissue biopsies. In studies 15, 17, and 19, liver tissue biopsies were performed on a subset of animals at the following time points: d 7, 14, and 28; d 1 or 2, 7, and 14; d 7, respectively. The method used was previously described by Lucy et al. (1998). Briefly, the skin was shaved and disinfected, and the area through the skin and body wall was anesthetized with 7 mL of 2% lignocaine (Lopaine 2%, lignocaine hydrochloride 20 mg/mL, Ethical Agents). A stab incision was made through the skin in the right 11th intercostal space at the level of the greater trochanter through which a 12-gauge \times 20-cm biopsy needle was inserted into the liver and approximately 200 mg (wet weight) of liver tissue was collected. Samples were stored at -80°C (studies 14 and 18) or at -20°C (study 16) until analysis.

Liver triacylglyceride content. In study 15, Gribbles Veterinary Pathology Ltd. analyzed triacylglycerides (**TAG**) content in liver biopsy samples (% of wet weight) by modifying the procedure described in the Wako LabAssay Triglyceride Kit (Wako Chemicals USA Inc.). Briefly, approximately 50 mg of liver tissue was finely chopped using a sterile scalpel blade and homogenized in 1 mL of 5% Triton-X100 in water. The homogenized tissue was slowly heated in a water bath (80 – 100°C) for 2 to

5 min or until the Triton X-100 131 appeared cloudy. After cooling the mixture at room temperature, the heating process was repeated one more time to solubilize all TAG into solution. The samples were vortexed and centrifuged at $2,000 \times g$ for 5 min to remove any insoluble material. The supernatant was collected in sterile 1.5-mL microfuge tubes and stored at -80°C . Approximately 50 μL of sample was diluted 10-fold with distilled water before the TAG assay. The TAG analysis was performed using the standard procedure provided in the Wako LabAssay Triglyceride Kit. In studies 17 and 19 the following alternative method was performed by Gribbles Veterinary Pathology Ltd.; briefly, liver samples were weighed and then digested overnight with 20% potassium hydroxide solution, followed by addition of H_2SO_4 to neutralize the potassium hydroxide, and addition of 3-[(3-cholamidopropyl)dimethylammonio]-1-propane-sulfonate to solubilize the TAG. The supernatant was then tested photometrically using the Triglycerides glycerol-3-phosphate oxidase-4-aminophenazone + 4-chlorophenol method (TG Kit, Roche Diagnostics) on the Roche Hitachi Modular P800 analyzer as per the manufacturer's instructions.

Uterine cytology and vaginal discharge score.

Uterine cytology. In studies 11 to 13 and 15 to 20, cytological samples of the endometrium were collected during early lactation (Table 2) as per the sampling frequencies described in the publications for each study (Table 1). For unpublished studies, sampling frequencies were: d 35 in study 17; at d 21 and 42 in study 19; and between d 8 to 16 and d 18 to 49 d post-calving in study 20. The endometrial sample collection procedure was previously outlined in (Burke et al., 2010b).

Recovered material was consequently smeared from the cytology brush onto a microscope slide and air dried. Slides were stained (Diff-Quick, Dade Behring Inc.) once completely dry and examined by a veterinary pathologist [studies 11 to 13, 15 to 16, and 19, Institute of Veterinary, Animal and Biomedical Sciences (IVABS), Massey University, Palmerston North, New Zealand; studies 17, 18, and 20, Dr. Dawn Seddon, Hamilton, New Zealand]. Areas of each slide that contained small clusters of epithelial cells (5 – 20 cells per cluster) were preferentially selected and all intact identifiable nucleated cells were counted in those fields. Approximately 200 (studies 11 to 13, 15 to 16, and 19) or 100 (studies 17, 18, 20) nucleated cells per slide were counted, with PMN cells distinguished from non-PMN cells to allow the percentage of PMN to be counted (Barlund et al., 2008; Burke et al., 2010b).

Vaginal discharge score. In studies 11 to 13 and 15 to 20, cows were examined for gross vaginal discharge during early lactation (Table 2) as per the sampling frequencies described in the publications for each study (Table 1). For unpublished studies, sampling frequencies were: between d 31 and 37 in study 16; at approximately 4, 21, and 42 d post-calving in study 19; and between d 8 to 16 and d 18 to 49 in study 20. The Metricheck procedure outlined in (McDougall et al., 2007) was used to score cows for gross vaginal discharge. The material within the concave surface of the device and/or adherent to the convex surface was scored on a 0 to 5 scale (0 = no discharge, 1 = clear mucus, 2 = flecks of purulent material within otherwise clear mucus, 3 = mucopurulent but <50% purulent material,

4 = mucopurulent with >50% purulent material and 5 = mucopurulent with >50% purulent material and with an odour). The device was rinsed in an antiseptic solution between cows (McDougall et al., 2007).